

NOTES

PAN systems precipitation of the complex was observed at $pH \approx 5.0$. Hence, the portion of the titration curves above these pH values could not be used for obtaining the formation function $\bar{n}$. In order to obtain stability constants the formation curves were drawn between $\bar{n}$ and pL . The approximate values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were obtained from the formation curves by reading them at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. The values were not considered to be reliable because $\log K_1/K_2 < 3.0$. Therefore, the values obtained have been further refined by least squares method. The values of stability constants are summarised in Table-2.

TABLE-2

METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT 25° AND $\mu=0.2$

System	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
In(III)-SDB	16.48	14.66
In(III)-CLM	17.09	14.87
In(III)-PAR*	12.54	11.46
In(III)-PAN*	12.19	10.57

*Experiments in 50% dioxan

Among the azo dyes the order in the stability constant values was found to be $CLM > SDB > PAR > PAN$. But the values of $\log K_1/\beta^H$ showed that the complexing tendency of PAR and PAN for In(III) was more than that of CLM and SDB. This may be due to the presence of stronger complexing group for In(III), like pyridyl nitrogen in the former ligands.

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References

1. A. P. JOSHI and K. N. MUNSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 1.
2. A. P. JOSHI and K. N. MUNSHI, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1968, **38**, 305.
3. A. P. JOSHI and K. N. MUNSHI, *Chimie Analytique*, 1969, **51**, 182.
4. A. K. BABKO and P. P. KISH, *Dop. Akad. Nauk Ukrain R.S.R.*, 1961, 1923.
5. A. I. BUSEV and M. IVANOV, *Izv. V. U. Z. M. V. O. S. S. R. Khim. i Khim. Tekhnol.*, 1961, **4**, 914.
6. C. D. DWIVEDI, K. N. MUNSHI, and A. K. DEV, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 248.
7. M. LANGOVA-HNIIICKOVA and L. SOMMER, *Talanta*, 1969, **16**, 681.
8. S. SHIBATA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1961, **25**, 348.
9. J. BJERRUM, "Metal ammine formation in aqueous solution", Heise: Copenhagen, 1941.
10. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.
11. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.

12. ERDEY LASZLO, "International Series of Monographs on Analytical Chemistry", Pergamon Press, 1965, p. 598.
13. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, 1971, p. 177.

Some Anionic Mixed-Ligand Complexes of Cobalt(II)

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THOUGH anionic complexes of cobalt(II) of the type $[CoX_4]^{-2}$, where X is halogen or pseudo-halogen have long been studied¹⁻⁵ in detail as typical tetrahedral compounds, little has been done to change the stereochemistry of these complexes by reacting with other nitrogen, oxygen or sulphur ligands. To increase the coordination number, particularly to synthesise compounds of coordination number five, we have been trying to synthesise anionic mixed-ligand complexes starting from these type of tetrahedral compounds. In this communication, we report a number of tetra-, penta- and hexacoordinated mixed-ligand (thiocyanate) complexes, using different ligand donor atoms.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. An ethanolic solution of cobalt thiocyanate was treated with an ethanolic solution of tetramethylammonium thiocyanate in 1 : 2 proportion when blue crystalline compound of ditetramethylammonium tetrathiocyanato cobalt(II) was separated out. This was then filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuo.

The mixed-ligand complexes were prepared, by adding requisite amount (1 : 2 ratio) of ligands separately to ethanolic suspension of ditetramethylammonium tetrathiocyanato cobalt(II) and refluxing for about 30 minutes. On cooling crystalline compounds were separated out which were then filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuo.

Metal and thiocyanate in the complexes were determined by complexometric E.D.T.A. method and nitrogen by micro analysis. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone medium using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurement were made over solid specimens by Gouy method. IR spectra were recorded on KBr phase using Perkin-Elmer-221 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded using M/100 (chloroform base) solution by Hilger-Watt U. V. Speck spectrophotometer. Relevant analytical, conductance and magnetic susceptibility and spectral data are given in Table 1.

TABLE—I ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA

Compounds	Colour and form	%cobalt		%N		%thiocyanate		$\Delta_{\text{mhos cm}^2}$	μ_{eff} (b.m)	mas (ϵ) k.k.
		Found	Reqd	Found	Reqd	Found	Reqd.			
[Me ₄ N][Co(SCN) ₅ DEA]	Deep blue crystalline	14.94	15.85	17.95	18.23	45.98	45.31	150	4.4	16.1 (1570) 8.0 (220)
[Me ₄ N][Co(SCN) ₅ (Quin)]	—do—	9.64	9.87	11.52	11.76	38.13	38.48	145	4.5	16.5 (1580) 8.1 (210)
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [Co(SCN) ₄ o-ph.D.A.]	Black crystalline	10.38	10.77	20.17	20.47	40.23	40.58	238	4.9	18.8 (40) 8.5 (20)
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [Co(SCN) ₅ Pdte]	Green crystalline	10.45	10.89	15.28	15.53	31.97	32.16	230	4.7	19.1 (61)
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [Co(SCN) ₅ Oxin]	—do—	10.83	11.20	15.72	15.99	32.95	33.29	245	4.7	19.0 (68)

DEA=Diethylamine, Quin=Quinaldine, o-ph.D.A.=o-phenylenediamine. Pdte.=Piperidyldithiocarbamate.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of analysis and conductance data, the complexes have the composition [L]₂[Co(NCS)₅B] where B is diethylamine and quinaldine; [L]₂[Co(NCS)₅B] where B is piperidyldithiocarbamate and oxin and [L]₂[Co(NCS)₄B] where B is o-phenylenediamine, and L is tetramethylammonium cation. The first category of complexes are deep blue in colour, have magnetic moments characteristic of typical tetrahedral cobalt(II) compounds and are 1:1 electrolytes as indicated by their conductance values (Table 1) in acetone medium. o-Phenylenediamine complex is a 2:1 electrolyte, is black in colour and has magnetic moment characteristic of an octahedral cobalt(II) species. The second type of complexes are green crystalline solids, 2:1 electrolytes and have magnetic moment values in between tetrahedral and octahedral cobalt(II) complexes.

In the infrared spectra absorption bands are noticed at 760(s), 955(vs), and 1490(vs) cm⁻¹ characteristic of the bands due to tetramethylammonium ion, modified due to complexation. Very sharp absorption bands are observed ~2050 cm⁻¹ attributable to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ of thiocyanate. In addition $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ bands have been observed at 1235 and 1200 cm⁻¹ for the thiocarbamate and oxin complexes. In case of the oxin complex $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ has disappeared indicating coordination of the oxin molecule through the hydroxyl oxygen. Evidence for the coordination of the bases have been further substantiated by appearance of bands ~360-370 cm and ~450 cm⁻¹ in the low frequency region assignable to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ (in case of oxin) respectively and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ at 260 cm⁻¹ for the dithiocarbamate.

In the electronic spectra of complexes with quinaldine and diethylamine two absorption bands are noticed ~16.0 and ~8.0 k.k. region attributable

to ${}^4\text{A}_g \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{P})$ and ${}^4\text{A}_g \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{F})$ transition respectively, the other transition is not observed probably because of its very weak intensity due to orbital selection rule. The high value of the ${}^4\text{A}_g \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{P})$ transition and magnetic moment values support a tetrahedral configuration for these two complexes. Two absorption bands are also observed for the o-phenylenediamine complex at 18.8(40) and 8.5(20) k.k. region attributable to ${}^4\text{T}_1(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{P})$ and ${}^4\text{T}_1(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_2$ transition. The intensity of the ${}^4\text{T}_1(\text{P})$ band and magnetic moment of the complex suggests a spin free octahedral configuration. Only one absorption band was noticed in ~19.1 k.k. region for complexes with dithiocarbamate and oxin, the other band probably being outside the range of spectrophotometer used. Intensity of this band is nearer to that of an octahedral complex, but from analysis, conductance and the comparative low magnetic moment value suggest these two complexes to be presumably penta-coordinated. This has been supported by an earlier report by Zinde *et al*⁶.

References

1. N. S. GILL and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem., Soc.*, 1959, 3997.
2. F. A. COTTON, D. M. L. GOODGAME and M. GOODGAME, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4690.
3. D. FORSTER and D. M. L. GOODGAME, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 1712.
4. F. A. COTTON, M. GOODGAME, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 1777.
5. A. TURCO, C. PEELE and M. NICOLINI, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 213.
6. R. N. MUKHERJEE, M. S. VENKATSHAW and D. M. ZINDE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 51.